

Visualizing social memory – How visual search engines structure the social memory

Robert Musil^a

^a *Università della Svizzera italiana, Via Giuseppe Buffi 13, 6900 Lugano, 473, Switzerland*

1. Introduction

Throughout most of human history, accessing various forms of social memory (or information retrieval) relied mostly on words. Be it oral communication or looking for books in a library, knowledge retrieval had to be structured around certain words from specific languages. Even until recently the accessibility of content, and even pictures, in search engines relied on the usage of keywords, and consequently, the assignment of keywords to the content by the information distributor. Visual search engines, like Google Lens or Pinterest Lens, change this premise. Information can now be accessed by taking or uploading pictures that are analyzed for visual cues and matched by an algorithm with corresponding similar or identical pictures. This shift has several social implications. Everyone can take the same picture of a bird or dress, and get similar results. The specific name for the bird and even the word for the color of the dress does not need to be known. Educational differences (Rózsa et al., 2015; Van Deursen & Van Dijk, 2011), like differing language use abilities, or skill level differences in search engine use (Hargittai, 2002) that still impact how well users are able to retrieve information (Lewandowski, 2016; Schultheiß & Lewandowski, 2021) can be flattened. At the same time, the information now becomes free of keywords in a sense because the visual cues (like color, shape, etc.) now determine what will be matched with certain pictures. Therefore, not only the way people access the social memory changes but also how it is structured in the background, meaning how it is curated in an index. Social research has largely ignored the impact of visual search engines on most levels of society. Research covering Pinterest, for instance, is about the technology of the visual search itself (Jing et al., 2015; Zhai et al., 2017) or the social platform as a whole (Hall & Zarro, 2012). The research on Google Lens is catching up on possible impacts it could have on a social level, like supporting art historians in their research, consumers in finding similar fashion items, or helping in educational settings (Salim et al., 2024; Shapovalov et al., 2019).

In my qualitative research, I want to dive deeper into how people make use of Google Lens and Pinterest in various ways, and how it enables them to access a visual social memory that would otherwise be inaccessible purely with text-based search queries. To do this, I will employ the Actor Network Theory (Callon, 2007; Latour, 2005) showing how user and device melt into one sociotechnical agencement equipped with the ability to navigate the social memory via the use of pictures, flattening educational differences, like language barriers. Simultaneously, I will try to advance the literature on social memory (Esposito, 2002) that has neglected visual access possibilities due to the unavailability of this technology until recently. Accessing the social memory just by pictures enables new opportunities (higher accessibility) and challenges (decontextualization of pictures).

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EMAIL: musilr@usi.ch (A. 1)

ORCID: 0009-0002-5855-0809 (A. 1)

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2. References

Callon, M. (2007). What does it mean to say that economics is performative? In D. MacKenzie, F. Muniesa, & L. Siu (Eds.), *Do economists make markets? On the performativity of economics* (pp. 311–357). Princeton University Press.

Esposito, E. (2002). *Soziales Vergessen: Formen und Medien des Gedächtnisses der Gesellschaft* [Social forgetting: Forms and media of the memory of society]. Suhrkamp Verlag.

Hall, C., & Zarro, M. (2012). Social curation on the website Pinterest.com. *Proceedings of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 49(1), 1–9.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/meet.14504901189>

Hargittai, E. (2002). Second-level digital divide: Differences in People's Online Skills. *First Monday*, 7(4). <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v7i4.942>

Jing, Y., Liu, D., Kislyuk, D., Zhai, A., Xu, J., Donahue, J., & Tavel, S. (2015). Visual search at Pinterest. *Proceedings of the 21st ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining* (pp. 1889–1898). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1505.07647>

Latour, B. (2005). *Reassembling the social: An introduction to actor-network-theory*. Oxford University Press.

Lewandowski, D. (2016). Suchmaschinenkompetenz als Baustein der Informationskompetenz [Search engine competence as a component of information literacy]. In W. Sühl-Strohmenger & M. Straub (Eds.), *Handbuch Informationskompetenz* [Handbook of information literacy] (pp. 115–126). De Gruyter Saur.

Rózsa, G., Komlodi, A., & Chu, P. (2015). Online searching in English as a foreign language. *Proceedings of the 24th International Conference on World Wide Web* (pp. 875–880). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2740908.2743007>

Salim, D. H., Susanto, J. J., Manalu, S. R., & Shiddiqi, H. A. (2024). Through the lens: Unveiling the power and promise of Google's visual search technology. *2024 International Conference on Information Management and Technology (ICIMTech)* (pp. 207–211). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIMTech63123.2024.10780912>

Schultheiß, S., & Lewandowski, D. (2021). (Un)bekannte Akteure auf der Suchergebnisseite? Ein Vergleich zwischen selbst eingeschätzter und tatsächlich vorhandener Suchmaschinenkompetenz deutscher InternetnutzerInnen [(Un)known actors on the search engine results page? A comparison between self-assessed and actual search engine competence of German internet users]. In T. Schmidt & C. Wolff (Eds.), *Information between data and knowledge: Information science and its neighbors from data science to digital humanities; Proceedings of the 16th International Symposium of Information Science (ISI 2021)* (pp. 218–246). Verlag Werner Hülsbusch.

Shapovalov, V., Shapovalov, Y., Bilyk, Z., Megalinska, A., & Muzyka, I. (2019). The Google Lens analyzing quality: An analysis of the possibility to use in the educational process. *Educational Dimension*, 1, 219–234. <https://doi.org/10.31812/educdim.v53i1.3844>

Van Deursen, A., & Van Dijk, J. (2011). Internet skills and the digital divide. *New Media & Society*, 13(6), 893–911. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444810386774>

Zhai, A., Kislyuk, D., Jing, Y., Feng, M., Tzeng, E., Donahue, J., Du, Y. L., & Darrell, T. (2017). Visual discovery at pinterest. *Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on World Wide Web Companion* (pp. 515–524). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1702.04680>